

DELAMINATION FRACTURE IN THE PRESENCE OF THROUGH-THICKNESS REINFORCEMENT

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SUMMARY: Fracture concepts are discussed for delamination cracks in laminates bridged by through-thickness reinforcement. By examining limiting crack configurations, a much simplified and general depiction of the problems of suppressing crack propagation (when through-thickness reinforcement is intact) and avoiding ultimate failure (when through-thickness reinforcement has failed) can be constructed. From these concepts, the paths towards material design principles and structural reliability codes diverge. For the former, deep insight is required into the micromechanics of the through-thickness reinforcement acting as bridging ligaments, which requires detailed experiments on failure mechanisms and models of failure phenomena. For the latter, a phenomenological solution is sought, in which bridging effects are represented by a function containing the fewest possible parameters that remains consistent with micromechanical models, with the parameters to be evaluated by a few properly chosen engineering tests. The details of this divided approach will be surveyed for the particular case of mode II delamination cracks in laminates reinforced by stitching.

KEYWORDS: delamination, stitching, z-reinforcement, rods, weaving, textiles, theory, fracture, micromechanics, crack bridging.

INTRODUCTION

Through-thickness reinforcement is the most promising method of solving the endemic problem of delamination in 2D laminates used as skins or sheets. It is also attractive for avoiding the pull-off of stiffeners or other attachments when out-of-plane tensile stresses arise. Various techniques of applying through-thickness reinforcement have been developed, including stitching [1-4], the insertion of short rods (so-called “z-reinforcement”) [5-8], and interlock weaving [9]. All of these approaches work in their primary goal, but they degrade in-plane properties to some extent, because of the disruption of in-plane fibers. It is therefore important to know the expected magnitude of the effect of through-thickness reinforcement, so that overdesign and unnecessary cost are avoided and in-plane properties maintained. The requisite models will be referred to here as material design models.

Once through-thickness reinforced composites are manufactured for a given application, a second engineering problem arises – the prediction of their strength, damage tolerance

(including notch and impact sensitivity), and fatigue lifetime. Models of the performance of the through-thickness reinforcement in a structure are required, which will be referred to here as structural reliability models.

This article outlines the elements of material design and structural reliability models for stitched laminates, mainly for polymer composites but with some reference to ceramic matrix composites. The central problem is the behaviour of delamination cracks that are bridged by stitching, which shields the delamination crack tip from the applied load by imposing tractions across the crack. In plane problems, the bridging tractions, p , include mode I and mode II tractions, p_3 and p_1 , where the x_1 is the direction of crack propagation and x_3 the through-thickness direction. The bridging tractions can usually be expressed as functions of the opening and sliding crack displacements, u_3 and u_1 .[♥] Structural reliability models deal with determining the essential characteristics of $p_i(u_j)$ from calibrating experiments and the question of how the crack will propagate given $p_i(u_j)$; material design models show how $p_i(u_j)$ depends on the material and geometrical properties of the constituent materials and the mechanisms by which individual bridging stitches act.

The nature of material design and structural reliability models for through-thickness reinforcement should be as distinct as their purposes. A material design model is intended to specify the details of the optimal reinforcement. It should therefore describe the mechanisms of the bridging action of the reinforcement and the failure of the laminate in detail, relating all macroscopic phenomena via micromechanics to the material and geometrical properties of the laminate and the through-thickness reinforcement. Fiber volume fractions, fiber orientations, reinforcement architecture, fiber and matrix properties (elastic and nonlinear), microcracking, crazing, the condition of interfaces, and fiber or tow pull-out effects are all phenomena that, among others, may appear explicitly in material design models; and whose investigation by innovative experiments, often on a microscopic scale, is demanded. No detail is too fine if it can be shown to influence the bridging relation, $p_i(u_j)$. A structural reliability model, in contrast, should be as simple as possible, retaining the minimum degrees of freedom necessary to generate accurate predictions of performance in a structural application. It should be coupled to a set of engineering tests by which it is to be calibrated. The structural reliability model should unburden the structural engineer of the need to know most of the details of why the through-thickness reinforcement acts in a certain way, preserving her from error by having a form known to be correct for the prevailing mechanisms. The calibrating tests must not be microscopic, but macroscopic, usually on specimens whose geometry reflects that of the structural component.

The problem of mode II delamination cracking will be used here as the prime example. Experimental results will be quoted for one exemplary laminate consisting of a quasi-isotropic lay-up (48 plies $[45/0/-45/90]_{ns}$), with an in-plane Young's modulus, $E_1 = 44.6$ GPa, transverse shear modulus, $G_{13} = 2.6$ GPa, and in-plane Poisson's ratios $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21} = 0.3$; stitches of doubled 3650 denier S-2 glass fiber tows on a square array of side 3.2 mm; individual stitch area = 0.636 mm^2 ; total stitch area fraction $c_s = 0.062$; and laminate half-thickness $h = 3.6$ mm [10,11]. Fracture concepts for bridged delamination cracks will be surveyed, experimental observations of mechanisms described, and material design and structural reliability models introduced.

[♥] In this paper, u_1 and u_3 are defined so that the total crack sliding and opening displacements are $2u_1$ and $2u_3$.

FRACTURE CONCEPTS

In work reported in detail elsewhere, end notch flexure (ENF) tests have been performed on numerous carbon/epoxy laminates stitched with Kevlar or glass fiber tows, including the exemplary case defined in the Introduction [12]. The ENF test configuration is illustrated in Fig. 1a. The specimen has thickness $2h$ and length $2L$ and contains a delamination crack of length a along its mid-plane. In a thin, unnotched and uncracked specimen of an orthotropic, homogeneous laminate, a load per unit width, P , generates uniform shear tractions of magnitude

$$\tau_a = \frac{3P}{8h} \tag{1}$$

along the mid-plane. In analyzing the fracture mechanics of an ENF specimen, either τ_a or P can be regarded as the independent variable. In this paper, τ_a will be used and referred to as the applied shear stress and the schematic shown in Fig. 1b will be examined. The shear tractions, p_1 , represent in a continuous approximation the bridging mechanisms developed by the stitches in the bridged portion of the delamination, $a-a_0$, a_0 being the length of the unbridged portion of the crack, e.g., a notch. The behavior of the ENF specimen is obtained by superposing the solution for the problem of Fig. 1b and the solution for a specimen containing no crack or notch and subject to the external load, P [13].

Fig. 1: The end notch flexure (ENF) test and coordinate system.

Fig. 2 shows crack opening and sliding displacements measured with great precision by stereoscopy along a typical delamination in an ENF specimen. The crack has grown from a notch and is bridged by stitches. The zone of detectable sliding displacement, which away from the notch is associated with a single interlaminar crack, extends some 20 mm from the notch. Its extremity indicates the position of the crack tip. The opening displacement is very small (effectively zero) within 2-3 mm of the mode II crack tip. Thus the tip conditions are pure mode II.[▼] The opening displacement rises to an approximately constant value in the

[▼] At a much finer scale, perhaps $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$, one might expect to find that the furthest advance of damage consists of arrays of ogive cracks, whose shapes are just such as to create pure mode I conditions at each of their crack tips when the far field stress is pure shear [14]. Such microcracks have been seen in similarly constrained layers of various brittle materials, including ceramics and epoxy resins [9]. However, the relevant scale for modeling the crack tip in Fig. 2 is $\sim 1\text{ mm}$, three orders of magnitude greater. At this scale, the stress fields must be almost entirely mode II, because the opening displacements are so much smaller than the sliding displacements.

crack wake. This is reminiscent of crack opening due to surface roughness in mixed mode fatigue crack tests in alloys. The plateau in the opening displacement corresponds there to the size of mismatched asperities. In the stitched laminates, the opening is due to the propping effect of the bridging stitches when they bend plastically within the crack. The crack of Fig. 2 remained bridged by intact stitches and propagated stably (increasing load) until it had reached the middle of the specimen. In other experiments, the stitches failed at the outset of crack propagation, which was then unstable. The nature of the fracture process depends critically on the laminate thickness, $2h$, the notch length, a_0 , and the nature of the stitching, which is embodied in the bridging law. For a mode II delamination, the bridging law is simply the dependence of shear bridging tractions, p_1 , on the sliding displacement, u_1 . For the crack of Fig. 2, p_1 may be regarded as continuous along the crack, rather than discrete, because the crack length is much greater than the stitch spacing.

Fig. 2: Total opening and sliding displacements for a delamination crack in a carbon/epoxy laminate stitched by S-2 glass fibers (from [12]).

Two limiting crack configurations characterize the various possible fracture histories. The first is the small scale bridging limit, where Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics prevails. The second will be referred to here as the ACK limit, in reference to the seminal work of Aveston, Cooper, and Kelly on mode I matrix cracks in fibrous composites [15]. A condition for the existence of the ACK limit is that the bridging law, $p_1(u_1)$, must be an increasing function. Experiments and models confirm that this is so.

The essential concepts introduced by the two limiting configurations can be summarized as follows (see [13] for details).

Small Scale Bridging Limit

If the bridging ligaments (stitches) fail during crack propagation, the delamination crack will eventually reach, in a sufficiently long specimen, a configuration characterized by a zone of intact stitches which is much smaller than the crack length, the notch size, and the specimen half length, L . The length of the bridging zone approaches a constant length, l_{SSB} , as the crack grows. In this limiting configuration the bridging stitches provide a constant increment, G_b , to the delamination fracture toughness of the composite, G_{II} :

$$G_{II} = G_{IIc} + G_b = G_{IIc} + 2 \int_0^{u_0} p_1(u_1) du_1 \quad (2)$$

where G_{IIc} is the delamination fracture energy of the unbridged composite and u_0 is the crack sliding displacement at which the bridging tractions vanish. The critical value, τ_{SSB} , of the applied shear stress, τ_a , in this limit follows through Griffith's energetic fracture criterion as

$$\tau_{SSB} = \frac{1}{a} \sqrt{\frac{h(G_{IIc} + G_b)}{\bar{A}}} \quad (3)$$

where a is the crack length; and \bar{A} is defined in [13] for general cases consistent with cylindrical symmetry in the ENF test and takes the value $\bar{A} = 4/E$ for the special but common case of a homogeneous, orthotropic laminate, with $E = E_1(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21})$. If either $p_1(0) \neq 0$ or $G_{IIc} \gg G_b$ (e.g., $G_{IIc} > 1.5 G_b$ for a linear law), then $l_{SSB} \sim (a_{IIc}h)^{1/2}$ where a_{IIc} is the mode II catastrophic length scale (a material constant):

$$a_{IIc} = \frac{4u_0}{p_0\bar{A}} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{G_{IIc}}{G_b}} - \sqrt{\frac{G_{IIc}}{G_b}} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

with p_0 and u_0 the values of p_1 and u_1 at bridging ligament (stitch) failure [13]. Eq. (4) reduces for a homogeneous orthotropic laminate with vanishing G_{IIc} to

$$\lim_{G_{IIc} \rightarrow 0} a_{IIc} = \frac{u_0 E}{p_0} \quad (5a)$$

and, in the particular case of a rectilinear bridging law, the quantity $2a_{IIc}$ in this limit coincides with the mode II characteristic length

$$l_{IIch} = \frac{G_b E}{p_0^2} \quad (5b)$$

for which a well-known analogy exists in mode I [13]. When $G_{IIc} = 0$, the notch sensitivity of the laminate, i.e., its loss of strength when an unbridged notch or delamination flaw of length a_0 is present, depends on $a_0/(l_{IIch}h)^{1/2}$. When $G_{IIc} \neq 0$, notch sensitivity and other fracture characteristics depend on both $a_0/(l_{IIch}h)^{1/2}$ and the ratio G_{IIc}/G_b .

If $p_1(0) = 0$ and G_{IIc} is relatively small, a realistic case for some stitched laminates, l_{SSB} no longer is approximated by $(a_{IIc}h)^{1/2}$, but becomes very large, rising in proportion to G_b/G_{IIc} ; but l_{SSB} still scales with $h^{1/2}$.

The ACK Limit

If the bridging ligaments (stitches) do not fail and $p_1(u_1)$ is an increasing function, the delamination crack will eventually, in a big enough specimen, reach a configuration in which

the applied shear tractions are sustained in the crack wake by equal and opposing bridging tractions and the critical stress for crack propagation, τ_{cr} , approaches a constant value, τ_{ACK} , given by [13,16]

$$G_{IIc} = 2 \left[\tau_{ACK} u_{ACK} - \int_0^{u_{ACK}} p_1(u_1) du_1 \right] \quad (6a)$$

where $\tau_{ACK} = p_1(u_{ACK})$. Equation (6a) reduces for a power law $p_1 = \beta u_1^\alpha$ to

$$\tau_{ACK} = \left[G_{IIc} \beta^\alpha \frac{1+\alpha}{2\alpha} \right]^{\frac{\alpha}{1+\alpha}} \quad (6b)$$

The ACK limit is approximated when the crack has propagated beyond any notch a distance $a - a_0$ somewhat greater than a length l_{ACK} given by

$$l_{ACK} = \sqrt{a_{IIIm} h} \quad (7)$$

$$a_{IIIm} = \frac{1}{A} \left(\frac{1+\alpha}{2\alpha} G_{IIc} \right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{1+\alpha}} \beta^{\frac{-2}{1+\alpha}} \quad (8a)$$

with the special case

$$a_{IIIm} = \frac{E}{4\beta} \quad (8b)$$

for linear bridging ($\alpha = 1$) in a homogeneous, orthotropic laminate [13]. When $a - a_0 \ll l_{ACK}$, bridging effects are weak and the crack propagates nearly as though it is unbridged, even though stitches already bridge the crack wake.

Characteristics of Fracture

Fig. 3 shows the evolution of the critical applied load for crack propagation in an ENF specimen with a notch (no stitches) of size a_0 when the bridging stitches never fail and the bridging law is linear. All curves share the asymptote $\tau_{cr} = \tau_{ACK}$. Crack propagation is unstable for small notches and stable for large notches. Defining a stable curve as one for which $\tau_{cr}(a_0) < \tau_{ACK}$, the minimum notch size for stable growth follows from Eqs. (3) and (8b) as $a_0 = (a_{IIIm} h)^{1/2}$.

Fig. 4 shows histories of the critical stress for one of notch sizes from Fig. 3 when the stitches have various finite strengths. If the stitches are strong enough (normalized strength 2.0 in the cases shown), the ACK limit is still reached without stitching failure. But for lower strengths, a period of growth without stitching failure is succeeded by stitching failure and unstable, catastrophic cracking. The specimen is rendered in two by the process. The critical stitch

strength for noncatastrophic cracking (towards the ACK limit) rises linearly with increasing notch size, a_0 , for large notches in a laminate of fixed depth, h (not as $a_0^{1/2}$, as it would in an infinite or very thick specimen). For small notches, whether cracking is noncatastrophic or catastrophic depends on the relative magnitudes of τ_{ACK} and p_0 ; or, equivalently, of the length scales a_{IIc} and a_{IIIm} [13].

The role of the length scale $(l_{IIch})^{1/2}$ in notch sensitivity is illustrated in Fig. 5, which shows how the notched ultimate strength of the laminate, τ_{ult} , depends on notch size for several bridging laws when the intrinsic delamination toughness, G_{IIc} , is zero. This will be a useful approximation in discussing the failure of stitches whenever $G_{IIc} \ll G_b$, which is probably always the case for bridged cracks in a ceramic matrix composite and will often be so in a textile polymer composite. [♦] The notch size is normalized by $(l_{IIch})^{1/2}$. When $a_0/(l_{IIch})^{1/2} > 1$, all curves converge, approaching the curve obtained for a Griffith crack in a material with toughness equal to that supplied by the bridging ligaments, G_b . Only when $a_0/(l_{IIch})^{1/2} < 1$ is there significant dispersion among the curves and even then it is modest. For vanishing notch size, the composite strength is limited by p_0 , the ligament strength. Thus $(l_{IIch})^{1/2}$ and p_0 alone are sufficient to define the ultimate notched strength to a fair approximation [13,17,18].

Fig. 3: Approaching the ACK limit in a mode II fracture test. The critical applied shear stress for delamination crack propagation in an ENF specimen for different notch sizes, with a linear bridging law and stitches that do not fail (from [13]).

When $G_{IIc} \neq 0$ (i.e., other than when $G_{IIc}/G_b \ll 1$, which may be the case in a composite with a tough polymer matrix), the ultimate notched strength will also depend quite strongly on G_{IIc}/G_b . It also then depends on the size of any initial bridged delamination crack (or matrix flaw). If the laminate is defect-free apart from the notch, its ultimate strength, $\tau_{ult}^{(max)}$, can be substantially higher than its ultimate strength, $\tau_{ult}^{(min)}$, in the presence of the most deleterious matrix flaw. This is illustrated for a material with a rectilinear bridging law and for a range of values of $G_b/G_{IIc} > 1$ in Fig. 6. Now the notched strength depends on p_0 , $(l_{IIch})^{1/2}$, and G_b/G_{IIc} .

[♦] Putting $G_{IIc} = 0$ is obviously not a valid step when modeling delamination crack growth, which must depend on the value of G_{IIc} , as illustrated, for example, by Eq. (6).

The concepts outlined here are of course not peculiar to mode II cracks or to delamination specimens. Similar length scales and nondimensional parameters control mode I fracture and apply to infinite specimens [18,19]. However, one important distinction of thin plates is that the lengths l_{ACK} and l_{SSB} are not material constants, as they are in infinite specimens, but material-structure parameters, involving the plate thickness, h .

Fig. 4: Catastrophic and noncatastrophic failure. If the stitches are strong enough, the ACK limit can still be reached. Otherwise, catastrophic failure sets in after some initial extension of the bridged zone.

Fig. 5: The ultimate notched strength for bridging laws of various shapes in a material with no intrinsic fracture resistance (from [13]).

THE MICROMECHANICS OF MODE II BRIDGING BY STITCHES

Experiments have now revealed the mechanisms of damage that develop in a bridging stitch as the crack sliding displacement increases. Direct observations of bridging stitches in the wake of a crack were obtained by sectioning a cracked ENF specimen [20]. The specimen, a carbon/epoxy laminate with S-2 glass stitches, was first encased, loading jig and all, in a block of epoxy resin while still under load. At this point it contained a delamination crack that had grown stably approximately 20 mm from a 20 mm notch. The petrified specimen was sectioned along its length and the section gradually polished down to reveal a sequence of stitches that ranged from far ahead of the crack tip to the furthest wake near the notch.

Fig. 6: Bounds for the ultimate notched strength corresponding to defect-free material and material in which a bridged delamination crack or matrix flaw already exists (from [13]). To the left of the circles on the curves for the upper bound, the ultimate strength is determined by crack initiation from the notch root; to the right by bridging stitch failure following stable propagation of a delamination crack to a finite length. The lower bound is determined by bridging stitch failure when an infinite delamination crack is presumed to exist in advance. The band shown for the lower bound covers curves for all values of G_b/G_{IIc} .

Ahead of the crack tip, the stitches were not visibly deformed or damaged. No microcracking or debonding was observed even around the last stitch in front of the crack tip. The first stitch behind the crack tip, i.e., the most recently enveloped in the crack wake, was exposed to some crack sliding displacement, but no significant opening displacement. Still no microcracking was visible around this stitch, but polarized light microscopy revealed a well demarked zone of crazing within it, extending over its whole diameter and approximately two stitch diameters away from the fracture plane on either side. Thus the stitch accommodated the crack sliding

displacement by internal plastic shear, presumed to be mediated by arrays of microcracks and crazing similar to those seen in other shear tests [9]. Stitches further back in the crack wake, where the sliding displacement was greater, had debonded from the surrounding laminate. The debond cracks involved no fiber/matrix separation, but consisted of matrix cracks that separated the stitch as a whole from the surrounding composite. They were most pronounced on the side of the stitch where local tensile stress would be expected. Around stitches subject to even greater crack sliding displacement (further back from the crack tip), significant plasticity and eventually splitting cracks and spalling were seen in the laminate.

Other observations of damage mechanisms were made during shear tests of small notched cubes cut out of a stitched laminate panel, each cube containing just one or two stitches [10]. The notch consisted of a square annular sawcut, which left a small, square island of unbroken material on the center plane of the cube. Each cube was cemented into massive, stiff grips, which were loaded in shear under displacement control. The load-displacement data from these tests should correspond directly to the bridging traction relation, $p_1(u_1)$, in the ENF specimen, with due account of volume fraction considerations. Representative results are reproduced in Fig. 7. The left ordinate is the shear stress within a stitch on the fracture plane, obtained by dividing the measured load by the cross-sectional area of the stitch (approximately 0.64 mm^2). The right ordinate is the corresponding bridging traction, p_1 , for a square array of stitches spaced 3.2 mm apart. It is obtained by dividing the measured load by the area occupied by a stitch in the array, i.e., $(3.2 \text{ mm})^2$, and does not depend on knowing the cross-sectional area of a single stitch.

Fig. 7: Shear load/sliding displacement data from four cuboidal specimens containing just one S-2 glass fiber stitch which were tested in stiff grips. The left ordinate shows the average shear stress across the stitch on the fracture plane; the right ordinate the equivalent bridging tractions for stitches on a square array with separation 3.2 mm . The displacement is the total displacement, $2u_1$. The heavy line shows the stress expected for the traction law deduced from the sliding profile of a crack in an ENF specimen. (Figure adapted from [10].)

Three of the curves in Fig. 7 show features and stress levels that are consistent with the deformation seen around stitches in the crack wake in the sectioned ENF specimen. (In the fourth curve, for which the peak load was only one third of that recorded for the other three, the stitch was probably damaged in advance during specimen machining.) At sliding displacements less than 0.2 mm, the shear stress in the stitch at the fracture plane (left ordinate) is just a few hundred MPa. For similar polymer composite plies under pure deviatoric shear, matrix microcracking leads to large strains at stresses above approximately 75 MPa, with hardening to ~ 100 MPa as the shear strain approaches 10% [9,21]. For the stitch to support loads well above 100 MPa, it must bend near the fracture plane so that significant load is carried in tension. But the degree of bending need not be very great to achieve equivalent shear stresses on the fracture plane of ~ 200 MPa, since the stitch has such a high axial stiffness. Thus plasticity and some stitch realignment will account for the total loads found below displacements $2u_1 < 0.2$ mm. For $2u_1$ between 0.2 and 0.6 mm, the curves consistently show a sharp drop. It is unclear yet whether this corresponds to the onset of the splitting cracks in the laminate as observed in the sectioned ENF specimen or debonding of the stitch from the laminate. Sliding displacements and total load then increase fairly smoothly to ultimate failure. The peak load is approximately 20% of that implied by the manufacturer's quoted tensile strength for S-2 glass. After failure the stitch is found to have dragged through the laminate only near the fracture plane, distorting onto a roughly sinusoidal locus. But the total crack sliding displacement at peak load is much larger than could be expected if the stitch stretched only in this region. Much of the crack displacement is evidently permitted by axial sliding of the stitch: there are pronounced dimples left on the outer laminate surfaces where the stitch has been pulled down towards the fracture plane. After peak load, there is a dramatic drop in load followed by some relatively small but enduring pullout forces.

BRIDGING LAWS FROM FRACTURE TESTS

Analysis of Crack Displacement Profiles

Bridging traction laws can also be deduced from measurements of crack displacement profiles such as those in Fig. 2. In the usual solution of the bridged crack problem for a mode II delamination, the crack sliding profile, $u_1(x_1)$, is calculated given an applied load, the crack geometry, and some particular law, $p_1(u_1)$, as one step towards computing the net crack tip stress intensity factor or, equivalently, G_{II} . The necessary calculations can be performed efficiently and accurately for most laminates by plate theory [13,22]. To deduce $p_1(u_1)$ from $u_1(x_1)$, this same problem is formulated as an inverse problem [12,23].

In solving inverse problems, special measures must usually be taken to treat experimental noise, since small oscillations in the data can lead to large oscillations in the deduced function, here the bridging law. The most expeditious technique was found to be the use of restricted parametric forms for the traction law [12], which is often recommended when data contain only enough information to reveal the general shape of the function being sought and not its details. Figure 8a shows a crack sliding profile obtained by stereoscopy, with typical experimental noise, together with the profile computed once the traction law had been deduced. The traction laws deduced from linear, quadratic, and cubic trial forms are shown in Fig. 8b. Their concurrence confirms that the law is essentially linear, the variance at the highest and lowest sliding displacements being due to the data being sparse at these extremes. The offset from the origin is real: trials with a linear law passing through the origin gave

markedly inferior agreement with the data. Once the traction law is determined, the intrinsic toughness, G_{IIc} , can be deduced from the critical load measured experimentally for the particular crack length.

Analysis of Load/Deflection Data

The measured relation between the magnitude of the point load applied to the ENF specimen and the load point deflection also contains information about the bridging traction law. The load/deflection record for the specimen for which the profile data of Fig. 8 were taken (in which a stable crack grew without failure of the stitching in the crack wake) is shown in Fig. 9a. The elastic response expected of an unnotched, uncracked specimen has been subtracted out of the displacement to highlight nonlinear behaviour. Figure 9b shows a hypothetical, parametric traction law which was used to compute the load/deflection curve for the specimen and notch configuration. The traction law parameters $p_1(0)$ and β and the intrinsic toughness, G_{IIc} , were varied to optimize agreement between the data and the prediction. The data show linear elastic behaviour at low loads, up to a knee corresponding to crack initiation at a load that depends on G_{IIc} and $p_1(0)$. The slope of the subsequent data, which show the specimen response as the crack is growing, depends on $p_1(0)$ and β .

Fig. 8: Bridging laws (b) obtained by fitting crack sliding profiles (a) from an ENF test of a carbon/epoxy laminate with S-2 glass stitches. (From [12].)

The fitted parameter values for the crack of Fig. 9 are $G_{IIc} = 0.2 \pm 0.03 \text{ kJ/m}^2$; $p_1(0) = 11. \pm 0.6 \text{ MPa}$; and $\beta = 110 \pm 11 \text{ MPa/mm}$. These are in excellent agreement with the traction law deduced from crack profile data (Fig. 8b), which is an entirely independent measurement. This agreement can be illustrated by using the values of G_{IIc} , $p_1(0)$, and β deduced from the crack profiles to reproduce the load/deflection data. The result is superimposed on Fig. 9a (fine dashed curve).

The deduced traction law can be converted to the average shear stress in a stitch on the fracture plane by dividing p_1 by the stitch area fraction, c_s . The result thus obtained from the linear law of Fig. 8a with the parameters inferred from load/deflection data has been superimposed as a heavy line on Fig. 7, the data from shear tests on miniature cuboidal specimens containing just one stitch. There is some discrepancy at the lowest displacements: the shear test data go to the origin, while the deduced traction law does not. However, the interval of displacements over which this causes disagreement is exaggerated by the data of

Fig. 7, because the test jig used for the cuboidal specimens had significant compliance, which was not subtracted from the recorded displacement. The true response of the material undoubtedly rises much more steeply from the origin than the data show. The traction law deduced from either crack profiles or load/deflection data should certainly be regarded as far superior in accuracy for displacements $2u_1 < 0.2$ mm. At higher displacements, the deduced traction law (dashed extrapolation) and the shear test data are in good agreement, since the latter also show an approximately linear increase with much the same slope. Again, entirely independent measurements concur.

Fig. 9: (a) Load/deflection data and fitted response for a specimen containing a crack that grew stably without stitching failure. The elastic response expected of an unnotched, uncracked specimen has been subtracted from the actual load point displacement. The dotted curve in (a) is a best fit to the data obtained by varying the trial traction law shown in (b) in a crack growth simulation. The fine dashed curve shows a similar simulation using the fixed parameter values deduced from crack profile analysis. All of the curves have been terminated at a maximum crack length of 53.6 mm.

BRIDGING LAWS AND LENGTH SCALES FOR ONE STITCHED LAMINATE

From the results of the preceding section for one particular carbon/epoxy laminate stitched with S-2 glass tows, values can be assigned to the bridging parameters and length scales introduced as fundamental constants.

Characteristics of the ACK limit

The concepts introduced in the first section for the ACK limit were defined by considering bridging laws satisfying $p_1(0) = 0$, whereas in the law deduced experimentally, $p_1(0) > 0$ (Fig. 8b and 9b). However, application of the J integral and stress superposition arguments show that the basic results require only trivial modifications. For the linear law of Fig. 9b, the ACK stress becomes

$$\tau_{ACK} = p_1(0) + \sqrt{G_{IIc}\beta}. \quad (9)$$

The critical stress curve shown for zero notch size in Fig. 3 is shifted up uniformly by $p_1(0)$. Therefore, l_{ACK} , of Eqs. (7) and (8) with $\alpha = 1$ will continue to prescribe the amount of crack

growth required for τ_{cr} to approach within a given amount of τ_{ACK} . Curves for nonzero notches will begin at the same point on the dotted curve (“no bridging”), but will now rise to the new, higher asymptotic value given by Eq. (9). With these changes, the qualitative appearance of all the critical stress curves remains much the same as shown in Fig. 3. In particular, a similar role in defining notch sensitivity is played by the length scale, a_{lim} , defined by Eq. (8a). The minimum value of $a_0/(a_{lim}h)^{1/2}$ required for stable crack growth will be somewhat lower, the criterion becoming

$$(10) \quad \frac{a_0}{\sqrt{a_{lim}h}} \geq \frac{1}{1 + p_1(0)/\sqrt{G_{IIc}\beta}}.$$

From the values deduced for G_{IIc} , $p_1(0)$, and β for the exemplary glass-stitched carbon/epoxy laminate, one obtains $\tau_{ACK} = 16$ MPa and $a_{lim} = 110$ mm. Since $h = 3.6$ mm, $l_{ACK} \approx 20$ mm. Thus from Eq. (10) a notch of length $a_0 > 6$ mm is required to obtain any stable delamination crack growth in an ENF specimen of this material; and somewhat larger than this for the stable growth to be readily observed. This indeed concurs with tests executed for various notch sizes. A specimen of half length $L > 100$ -150 mm would be required to produce a crack that had approached close to the ACK limit. The analysis of crack growth in ENF tests in specimens of typical size would therefore require full solution of the bridged crack problem; no asymptotic solution would be adequate.

Characteristics of the Small Scale Bridging Limit

The traction laws of Fig. 7 contain all information required to characterize the small scale bridging limit. The total work of fracture, the area under the curves computed with the right hand ordinate, is $G_b \approx 30$ kJ/m². This is about two orders of magnitude greater than the intrinsic mode II fracture toughness of the laminate, $G_{IIc} \approx 0.2$ kJ/m². In any test in which the crack is in or near the small scale bridging limit, the influence of G_{IIc} will be virtually undetectable. While G_{IIc} was evaluated successfully by analyzing cracks approaching the ACK limit, it could not be measured by experiments on cracks propagating near the small scale bridging limit.

Again referring to the right hand ordinate of Fig. 7, one has $p_0 \approx 55$ MPa; while the critical sliding displacement $u_0 \approx 0.6$ mm. Equation (5b) then gives $l_{IIch} \approx 500$ mm. For $h = 3.6$ mm, $(l_{IIch}h)^{1/2} \approx 40$ mm. Since $G_{IIc} \ll G_b$, the quantity $(l_{IIch}h)^{1/2}$ will control the notch sensitivity of ultimate strength, much as shown by the curve for a rectilinear law in Fig. 5; and the equilibrium zone length in small scale bridging will be given to within a factor near unity by $l_{SSB} \approx (l_{IIch}h)^{1/2}$. Thus a specimen of half length L much higher than 300-400 mm would be required to achieve small scale bridging conditions. This will not be the case in specimens of common dimensions; and therefore full solution of the bridged crack problem rather than asymptotic approximations (i.e., in this regime, linear elastic fracture mechanics) is again required for fracture analysis. In particular, unless an especially long specimen is used, it will not be accurate to quote a single value for the composite fracture toughness, $G_{II} = G_{IIc} + G_b$, deduced by linear elastic fracture mechanics from a strength measurement. Unfortunately, this error has already taken up residence in the literature.

The Transition from Noncatastrophic to Catastrophic Failure

For a material in which $G_{IIc} \ll G_b$, the strength of an unnotched specimen will be approximately p_0 [13].* If $p_0 > \tau_{ACK}$, the ACK limit could then be approached, with a delamination crack fully bridged by intact stitches propagating noncatastrophically right across the specimen. However, if a large enough notch is present, the stress concentration at the notch root will cause the stitches to fail there before the applied shear stress reaches τ_{ACK} and failure will be catastrophic (i.e., the first crack will separate the specimen in two). For the material analyzed above, $\tau_{ACK}/p_0 = 16/55 = 0.3$. From Fig. 5, the transition from noncatastrophic to catastrophic failure will therefore be expected when $a_0/(l_{IIch}h)^{1/2} \approx 1.25$ or $a_0 \approx 50$ mm. Since this length is substantially greater than l_{ACK} , there are in this case smaller notch sizes for which stable noncatastrophic cracks can be expected. This is obviously so, as the results above demonstrate. However, there could be other materials in which the opposite would hold, that a notch large enough for stable delamination crack growth (i.e., $\tau_{cr}(a_0) < \tau_{ACK}$) would also be large enough for stitch failure, in which case an experimenter would search in vain for stable delamination cracks (see also Fig. 4).

The Effect of the Discreteness of Stitches

The length scales, l_{ACK} and l_{SSB} , provide a simple test of the validity of representing the effect of discrete stitches as continuous tractions: they must be much greater than the stitch spacing, d . If the stitches do not fail in the crack wake, then the bridging tractions become significant compared to the applied shear stress when the crack length, a , is somewhat greater than l_{ACK} (Fig. 3). If d is much less than l_{ACK} , then many stitches will already be involved in this stage of crack growth. For the material studied in detail above, this is the case: $d = 3.2$ mm while $l_{ACK} = 20$ mm. This also implies that stitching can have little effect in this material in suppressing the initiation of delamination cracks (i.e., the generation of cracks just a few mm long). The material relies mainly on the intrinsic delamination toughness, G_{IIc} , for resistance to crack initiation.

If the stitches do fail, then l_{SSB} is the relevant length scale. Once again, for the material taken as an example here, $d \ll l_{SSB}$ and the effects of the discreteness must be negligible. Many stitches are involved in the bridging zone and the sliding displacement experienced by the ultimate stitch must be very close to the sliding displacement calculated in the continuous traction model.

Friction on the Delamination Fracture Surfaces

Stitching does not inhibit delamination crack initiation by its action as a crack bridging entity. However, once a crack of length several mm exists, other shielding mechanisms might play an important role, especially friction arising from fracture surface roughness, and stitching has important indirect roles in determining friction. The stitching process introduces waviness in the in-plane plies, forcing the delamination fracture surface to be non-planar; and stitching restricts mode I crack opening, keeping the fracture surfaces in contact over a zone behind the crack tip that is longer than it might be in the absence of stitching. Experiments are in order to quantify these effects. Figure 2 suggests that, since the crack exhibits mode I opening at distances more than 2-3 mm from the mode II crack tip, fracture surface friction effects

* When $G_{IIc} \neq 0$, there will be in a material that behaves strictly according to the model defined in this paper, a regime of small notch sizes where stitch failure must be preceded by matrix crack initiation at a stress higher than p_0 , rising for small notches as a_0^{-1} .

operate over a zone much smaller than the bridged zone over which the stitches act. It should therefore be valid for cracks longer than a few mm to include friction effects as an enhanced value of the intrinsic fracture toughness, G_{IIc} . Further, when friction can be included in G_{IIc} and G_{IIc} is evaluated either by inverting a crack sliding displacement or by fitting load/deflection data, as reported above, the deduced value will already include the effects of friction. They are inseparable from other contributions to G_{IIc} for such measurements under these conditions.

STRUCTURAL RELIABILITY MODELS

Consider the engineering task of predicting the failure of a stitched laminate component in service. To simplify the discussion and relate it directly to the results summarized above, assume that the applied load is expected to create shear on the delamination plane and that the delamination crack is therefore a mode II crack. Of course, arbitrary applied loads might generate mixed mode conditions, but the approach to be outlined here can be generalized.

The material data from which delamination failure can be calculated are the elastic constants of the laminate, which can be regarded as known; and the intrinsic delamination fracture resistance, G_{IIc} , and the bridging traction law, $p_1(u_1)$, which must be determined. The traction law, $p_1(u_1)$, will represent the entire contribution of the stitches to delamination suppression by crack bridging. The essential step is to recognize just which characteristics of $p_1(u_1)$ need to be known and to define simple tests for their evaluation.

Noncatastrophic Cracking

Figure 3 shows that, in the absence of a notch, the ACK stress, τ_{ACK} , provides a conservative bound for the applied shear stress required for noncatastrophic delamination cracking (crack growth without accompanying stitch failure). Thus τ_{ACK} defines the proportional limit for the structure as long as delamination cracking is the first failure mechanism. (The ACK stress already serves in a similar function for engineering applications of ceramic matrix composites under aligned tensile loads, in which the first nonlinearity is the appearance of multiple mode I matrix cracks [24].) The delamination cracking stress is not reduced by the pre-existence of a delamination crack, provided it remains fully bridged by essentially undamaged stitches. For parts containing bridged delamination flaws, τ_{ACK} is a design limit.

However, if a notch exists over which the stitches have been cut – or perhaps an impact damage zone exists in which the stitches have been weakened or destroyed during the creation of a delamination crack – the stress for noncatastrophic delamination cracking, τ_{cr} , may be less than τ_{ACK} . For a bridging law like that shown in Fig. 9b, Eq. (10) specifies the critical notch size above which $\tau_{cr} < \tau_{ACK}$. Thus the controlling parameters are τ_{ACK} , $p_1(0)$, and the structure-material length scale, l_{ACK} ; or equivalently, $p_1(0)$, β , and G_{IIc} . These three degrees of freedom are all the material properties that are needed to predict the delamination performance of the part under shear loading, provided no stitches fail during the crack propagation.

To evaluate the controlling parameters and predict noncatastrophic delamination, detailed knowledge and micromechanical models of the bridging process are not required. It is enough to determine τ_{ACK} , $p_1(0)$, and l_{ACK} (or $p_1(0)$, β , and G_{IIc}) empirically. A simple and sufficient experiment would appear to be a record of load/deflection data, such as Fig. 9a.

Catastrophic Delamination

The two essential characteristics of the traction law $p_1(u_1)$ for predicting stitch failure are the peak traction, p_0 , and twice the area under $p_1(u_1)$, which is the bridging contribution to the work of fracture, G_b . Figure 5 shows that further details of the shape of $p_1(u_1)$ have negligible effect on the load at which stitches fail.

Once again, it would appear that standard ENF tests should be sufficient to evaluate these parameters. A sequence of tests with increasing notch size should replicate Figure 5; information about p_0 is contained mainly in the intercept at zero notch size and about G_b in the slope of the curve.

In laminates in which G_{IIc} is comparable to or greater than G_b , the notched strength diagram of Fig. 5 must be modified to account for the actual value of G_{IIc} [13]. But the same sequence of tests should still suffice for evaluating p_0 and G_b , which continue to be sufficient information about the bridging law for predicting catastrophic cracking..

MATERIAL DESIGN MODELS

Consider next the problem of selecting the quantity and nature of stitching tows to achieve target engineering properties in a structure, i.e., for shear loading, to achieve particular

characteristics in the traction law, $p_1(u_1)$. This is a question which demands complete modeling of the bridging process. It must be approached by considering the mechanisms of deformation of discrete stitches.

For stitches deforming in shear caused by crack sliding displacement, the mechanisms are highly nonlinear, complex, and only partially revealed by the experiments reported above (and more fully in [10] and [20]). Further experiments are needed to detail plasticity, the patterns of cracks that form around a stitch as it shears, the mechanics of stitch rupture, and the process of pullout of the stitch, which evidently begins before its rupture. With due experimental grounds, models may then be formulated to study the roles of stitching fiber properties, matrix properties, stitch size, stitch orientation, etc. Such work is in progress.

These material design models are necessarily much more complex than structural reliability models. The material and geometrical parameters that can affect $p_1(u_1)$ may be very numerous. The details must be pursued. However, it is very important to recognize that all the same details need not be carried on to the problem of formulating structural design models. As explained above, structural design models address a much more restricted question with consistently limited information about the bridging process.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are very grateful to Mr. Larry Dickinson for supplying stitched laminate specimens; Dr. Fred Morris for stereoscopic analysis of images; and Dr. Stefan Janssen for initiating the tests of cuboidal specimens. BNC was supported by AFOSR Contract Number F49620-94-C-0030; RM and DM by Rockwell Independent Research and Development

Funds; and AT and KW by Pratt and Whitney Aircraft under a Technology Reinvestment Project with the Advanced Research Projects Agency.

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